

ENTROPY IN A CONTRACTING UNIVERSE

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Abstract

We examine the change of entropy in a contracting universe. If the space of the universe, together with its mass and energy, is contracting, in the end the more probable situation is that its whole thermodynamic system contracts into fewer possible microstates. Entropy is decreasing. The 2nd law of thermodynamics changes. This is opposite to what happens in our expanding universe. There are obvious important consequences for physics and cosmology.

Résumé

Nous examinons le change d'entropie dans un Univers contracté. Masse et énergie contractent dans cet Univers. Si l'espace contracte, le système thermodynamique de l'Univers contracte aussi. Finalement, il y a moins de microétats possibles. Entropie est diminué. C'est le contraire de ce qui arrive a notre Univers qui s' expande. Les conséquences possibles pour la physique et la cosmologie pouvaient être importantes.

Keywords: entropy, laws of thermodynamics, contracting universe, cosmology

In cosmology, we often treat the “Universe” as an isolated system, typically the observable Universe or a large comoving volume. Such a system is finite and isolated, so we can speak about its entropy.

We know that entropy continuously increases in our expanding Universe.

The importance of entropy consists in that it is central to the second law of thermodynamics, which states that the entropy of an isolated system left to spontaneous evolution cannot decrease with time. As a result, isolated systems evolve toward thermodynamic equilibrium, where entropy is higher. Entropy increase, under certain conditions of the Universe (homogeneity etc), which are considered to be valid in our Universe. entails the second law of thermodynamics

Why does entropy increase in our Universe? Some authors state that the main reason is the ionizing radiation of the stars. This may be reasonable now. But we know that entropy increased even when stars did not exist. Some calculations show that the main increase of the Universe’s entropy occurred during its initial inflationary expansion (1). This increase is obviously due to the Universe’s expansion.

Generally speaking

$$S = k \ln \Omega \text{ (Equation 1),}$$

where Ω represents the maximum number of microscopic ways in which the macroscopic state corresponding to S can be realized.

In the case of ideal gases, an increase in volume of the closed thermodynamic system by two, without change in the mass and energy of the system, will lead to an increase of its initial entropy by $\ln 2$. This is valid for isothermal expansion of reversible processes and all irreversible processes. Entropy remains stable only in reversible, adiabatic processes, where usually the volume of the system remains stable.

The same increase in entropy with increase of the volume is valid for all parts of our Universe. The main constituent of the Universe's actual entropy is the entropy of the black holes, especially the giant ones. We cannot discuss black holes in depth without a theory of quantum gravity, which does not exist. For example, we do not know why the entropy of the black holes is analogous to their surface and not their volume (2), even if some relevant ideas have been proposed. But we can say that according to the Hawking's Area Theorem, the total area of black hole horizons never decreases (classically). This corresponds to increasing entropy.

Gravitational entropy is not well defined and described, but we can say that it also increases in our expanding universe. So, we know that the extended 2nd law is valid for the black holes and gravitational entropy (3).

Another very important part of the Universe's entropy is the entropy of the cosmic horizon (dominant in the far future in an accelerating universe). **De Sitter entropy** represents the **maximum possible entropy** (i.e., information content) for a causally connected region in a dark-energy-dominated universe. This part of entropy also increases with increased space (4).

In cosmology, gravitational entropy plays a key role in early-universe and structure formation scenarios. The Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) is extremely uniform, indicating a very *low gravitational entropy* initial state. As time evolves, tiny density fluctuations grow under gravity into the cosmic web of filaments, galaxies and clusters. This clumping of matter corresponds to a growth of gravitational entropy.

We can say that “the entropy of matter in the universe is due to gravitational clumping of matter; as matter clumps, the entropy increases and the maximal entropy occurs for the extreme case of a black hole” In line with Penrose's Weyl curvature hypothesis,

the Weyl tensor was effectively zero at the Big Bang and grows with time, tracking the increase in gravitational entropy (5).

There are some papers measuring the total entropy of its entropy. They measure its constituent parts and then add them to the final result. For two independent subsystems A and B (with no interaction), the total number of microstates is multiplicative:

$\Omega_{A+B} = \Omega_A \Omega_B$ because one can choose a microstate of A and a microstate of B independently. Consequently, the Boltzmann entropy is additive under certain circumstances (6). Their measurement of all parts of the entropy of the Universe is done by the equations valid for the entropy of each part and then multiplying them with the volume of the part and adding the entropies of all parts together.

Key assumptions in summing cosmic entropies include isolation, independence of the parts, coarse graining and general relativity.

Even if this technique is not completely sure, it is reasonable that all parts of the entropy of the Universe increase together with the volume of the universe.

Microstates can be studied as quantum or classical microstates. In quantum microstate, each quantum state is a separate and distinct microstate of the system. In classical microstates, we use phase space of position q and momentum p coordinates. In such a case, a microstate is a volume element in a $6N$ -dimensional phase space of N particles. It is then obvious that the number of possible microstates increases with the volume of the system.

We can then say that entropy change is fundamentally an increase in the dispersion of energy and if we want to introduce a molecular thermodynamic explanation for the increase in entropy with volume we can state that a greater dispersion or spreading of

the original, unchanged amount of energy within the system is caused because there are more closely spaced microstates in the new larger volume (7). It is obvious that in an expanding Universe there are more possible microstates, so increasing entropy is more probable.

It is obvious that equation 1 is in reality stochastic. This is more obvious in the Gibbs definition of entropy;

$$S = -k_B \sum p(i) \ln(p(i)) \quad (\text{Equation 2}).$$

This equation is considered to be valid in closed and homogeneous systems, such as our Universe, The system is closed because there is no heat exchange with the outside. The problem of homogeneity is tackled by the addition of its constituent parts, as we have already described.

We conclude that entropy can change through many processes in our universe, but the intrinsic expansion of its space leads to its tendency to increase.

We would like to pose a theoretical question. What happens with entropy in a contracting Universe? The usual answer is that entropy change does not have to do with the expansion or contraction of the Universe, so that the relevant laws remain the same and entropy will continue to increase.

But I do not believe that this is the case. Let us suppose that the Universe starts to contract today or in the future. It starts with high entropy and continuously contracts. It will finally reach a state analogous to the pre-big bang state of our Universe. In this state, entropy is minimal. The reasonable conclusion is that entropy decreases in a contracting Universe.

How can this happen? We know that for a given set of macroscopic variables, entropy measures the degree to which the probability of the system is spread out over different possible microstates. We can see this in Equation (1).

Mass and energy contract in a contracting Universe. If space is contracting, the more probable situation is that the system contracts into fewer possible microstates. It is obvious that in a contracting Universe there are fewer possible final microstates, so decreasing entropy is more probable. We have no experimental evidence for such a fact, but we have the mathematical certainty of equation (2).

This is the reason why entropy in a contracting Universe decreases.

Universe expansion or contraction is imperceptible in our everyday life. If we measure how minimal the expansion of the space in relationship to the existing space is (8) and that according to equation 1, entropy increases logarithmically in relationship to the volume, we can understand that the effect of this mechanism to the evolution of entropy is infinitesimal. It is thus reasonable that experimental evidence is compatible with the supposition that entropy increase does not depend on Universe expansion or contraction. If the Universe starts to contract, there will be no sudden change of the laws of Physics. The difference in the volume of the Universe, and even more its entropy, will be imperceptible initially to us. When and how the effect of Universe contraction on decreasing entropy will be perceived or determining, could possibly be studied. If we look long term and at the big picture of the whole Universe, it is inevitable that finally entropy will start to decrease and the 2nd law of thermodynamics will change accordingly.

We can hence see that star ionization is allowed by the favorable condition of increasing entropy in our Universe. In a contracting Universe, other processes, favored by its decreasing energy, will finally appear.

Entropy is defined as

$dS=dQ/T$ (Equation 3).

If heat Q is constant in our Universe (no heat is exchanged between the Universe and outside) and temperature generally decreases with time, it is obvious that entropy increases. Exactly the opposite occurs in a contracting Universe, where the temperature increases.

According to equation 2, entropy measures the state of randomness or disorder. We can also describe such spreading out of energy as dispersal, which leads to loss of the differentials required for work even though the total energy remains constant in accordance with the first law of thermodynamics (9).

If we return back to a contracting Universe, we can observe that temperature increases, so that, according to equation 3, it is reasonable that entropy decreases. If our statement holds, the laws of physics, especially the second law of thermodynamics, change and the physical consequences are immense. According to equation (1), it is expected that entropy will continuously decrease in a contracting Universe. According to equation (3) the temperature of the contracting Universe will continuously increase.

The second law of thermodynamics of our expanding universe can be stated as;

“A transformation whose only final result is to transfer heat from a body at a given temperature to a body at a higher temperature is impossible”. This law cannot be true in a contracting universe whose temperature spontaneously increases. In such a universe, heat spontaneously transfers from a lower temperature body to a higher temperature body. This is the reversal of the 2nd law.

The fundamental thermodynamic relationship (it implies some thermodynamic conditions that are valid in general)

$$dU = TdS - PdV \text{ (Equation 4)}$$

does not have to change, but entropy changes direction.

Weyl curvature hypothesis does not hold for the contracting universe. Finally, Weyl tensor and big crunch entropy are minimal.

Under certain conditions, the initial state of the Universe could be reconstructed, without attrition.

Entropy is the only quantity in the physical sciences that seems to imply a particular direction of progress, sometimes called an arrow of time. As time progresses, the second law of thermodynamics states that the entropy of an isolated system never decreases in large systems over significant periods of time. According to our opinion, the arrow of time is not caused by the 2nd law of thermodynamics, but conforms to it in an expanding Universe. This same arrow of time conforms to the new 2nd law in a contracting Universe.

It is obvious that, if our hypothesis is correct, the problems with the Lohsmidt reversibility objection (10) and with Zermelo's criticism that a system cannot be monotonic and recurrent (11) are solved.

The physical meaning of entropy does not change in a contracting Universe. It continues to measure the state of randomness. The difference is that now, the most probable situation is the decrease in the number of microstates and hence the diminution of entropy in time.

I do not know if the existence of a contracting Universe is possible. Our experimental facts show that not only the Universe expands, but also that its expansion is accelerating.

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